

THERMORHEOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERFACIAL BONDING ENHANCEMENT OF BASALT FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES

J.S. Kim¹, S.Y. Mun², H.M. Lim³, and D. Lee⁴

¹Department of civil engineering, ERI, Gyeongsang National University, Jinju, 52851, South Korea, jskim@gnu.ac.kr

²Fibrous ceramics and aerospace materials center, Korea Institute of Ceramic Engineering and Technology, Jinju, 52851, South Korea, msy@kicet.re.kr

³Fibrous ceramics and aerospace materials center, Korea Institute of Ceramic Engineering and Technology, Jinju, 52851, South Korea, lim@kicet.re.kr

⁴Department of polymer science and engineering, Chonnam National University, Gwangju, 61186, South Korea, dlee@chonnam.ac.kr

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ABSTRACT

Strong interfacial bonding between reinforcing inclusions and polymer matrix is of great interest since load transfer between two different phases is significantly affected by their interfacial bonding behaviors. In order to enhance the load transfer from the matrix to the fibers, thermomechanical properties of composites need to be clarified. The weak interfacial bonding properties of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are attributed to poor compatibility between the polar hydrophilic fibers and the non-polar hydrophobic polymer matrix with a weak interfacial adhesion between the fibers and the polymer matrix. Plasma treatment has been proved to a versatile tool for the physical modification of reinforcing fillers in the composites without environmental harms in comparison with using chemical treatment of fiber surfaces. Basalt fibers have become a potential candidate owing to their high modulus and strength, good heat and chemical resistance, and outstanding isolation against vibration. Nonetheless, the existence of interphase as a region intermediate between the two phases is a critical issue for the interfacial bonding enhancement. Here, we study the thermorheological properties of basalt fiber reinforced epoxy composites by dynamic mechanical analysis to investigate the interphase region. The purpose of this study is to investigate the synergistic effect of plasma treatment with various sizing agents for the basalt fiber reinforced epoxy composites from the viewpoint of wettability, surface chemistry, and viscoelasticity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The dynamic mechanical and viscoelastic properties of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites depend not only on the property of each primary component but also on the nature of fiber surface, interfacial bonding strength between fibers and resin, and load transfer at the interface/interphase [1]. The strong interface between fibers and polymer matrix is essential to improve load transfer from the matrix to the fibers and thereby to enhance the thermomechanical properties of the composites [2]. Poor thermomechanical properties of FRP composites are attributed to reduced compatibility between the polar hydrophilic fibers and the non-polar hydrophobic polymers, with weak interfacial adhesion between the fibers and the polymer matrix. The strong interfacial bonding between the fibers due to strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding is also an additional cause for poor interfacial properties.

Plasma treatment offers a new strategy for the modification of reinforcing fibers in the composites allowing clean and dry processes without environmental harms that is critical concerns when using chemical treatments of fiber surfaces although the chemical reaction is successful in improving the interfacial bonding between the fibers and the matrix. In principle, the chemical treatments of fiber surfaces facilitate the penetration of epoxy into the hydrolyzed silane, producing a possible formation

of entanglement that may increase the rigidity and decrease the degree of phase separation of the two components [3]. The act of plasma on the fibers can modify the surface of the materials without deteriorating their bulk properties [4]. Incomplete wetting may produce interfacial defects and reduces the interfacial shear strength by flaw-induced stress concentration. The plasma treatment can also enhance the wettability that considerably affects the interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the matrix. With the aid of plasma treatment, surface energy can either be increased or decreased, crosslinking can be introduced, and reactive free radicals can be produced on the exposed materials.

Among currently used fibers for FRP, glass fiber has several drawbacks such as surface damage and high sensitivity to alkaline conditions. To overcome these issues, basalt fiber (BF) has become a potential candidate for FRP composites owing to its high modulus and strength, good heat and chemical resistance, and outstanding vibration isolators [5]. BF extruded from melted basalt rock shows at least 16% higher modulus, equivalent tensile strength, and better heat and chemical resistance in comparison with E-glass fiber. BF reinforced composites have great potential as construction and transportation materials to replace steel and glass fiber wherever corrosion problems exist such as exposure to salt water, alkaline attack, ocean climate, etc. Nonetheless, there are still existing issues that interphase between the BF and the polymer matrix may control the overall dynamic mechanical and viscoelastic behaviors of these systems because the poor interphase may cause severe failure upon loading in long-term service.

The existence of interphase as a region intermediate to two contacting solids has been gaining much attention, which is distinct in structure and properties from either of the two contacting solid phases [6]. Interphases exist in macro and microsystems such as FRP composites, adhesive joints, and coating systems. The interphase is deliberately built into the composite by treating the surface of fibers. The interphase region may have different properties from the bulk matrix and the fillers and the level of fiber to matrix adhesion directly affects the dynamic mechanical properties of composites. It is, therefore, important to understand fundamentals on the interphase region and the magnitude of its influence for the prediction and control of composite properties.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) is a useful technique known for its sensitivity in the detection of inhomogeneity in polymer and composite morphologies. Elastic modulus and internal damping are crucial parameters and are measures of the stiffness and energy dissipation ability of materials.[10,21] Specially, a damping property of composites is a sensitive probe of a wide variety of molecular motions, relation processes, thermal transitions, and structural homogeneities, all of which affect thermomechanical behavior of materials. In general, the molecular motions in composites at the interfacial region contribute to material damping, broadening the damping peak. The damping peak of fiber reinforced composites is shifted to a higher temperature compared to that of the pure matrix, which indicates reduced mobility of molecular chains in the presence of fibers. Therefore, the estimation of damping will enable to investigate the interphase region and to quantify the interfacial bonding. This work aims to seek the coupling effect of plasma treatment with various sizing agents for BFRP composites from the viewpoint of wettability, surface chemistry, and viscoelasticity. We examine whether interphase may be tailored to enhance the interfacial bonding strength in the composites.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials and preparation

Basalt fiber supplied by YJC with a diameter of about 17 μm was used in this work. Melamine (M-85, Daeyang), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, RIFA Co.), bisphenol-A epoxy resin (YD-128, Kukdo Chem.) were used as a sizing agent. The matrix used to prepare basalt fiber reinforced epoxy composite was a bisphenol-A resin combined with a curing agent (G-A0435) both of which were supplied by Kukdo Chemical Co. The surface of the commercial basalt fibers was cleaned by heating at 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under nitrogen for 6h. The basalt fiber was ground to a length of about 50-200 μm . Air plasma treatment (45 W, 0.2torr) was performed to form hydroxyl groups on the surface of the basalt fiber. The sizing of the non-plasma treated basalt fiber of plasma treated basalt fiber was performed by diluting melamine, PVA, epoxy in 1 wt% solution, respectively. A small amount of basalt fiber was mixed by a paste mixer in 3 gram of epoxy resin and 1.5 gram of hardener for 1 min with 3000 rpm. The mixture was

transferred into a mold and held in a vacuum oven at 25 °C for 3 h to remove air bubbles. The uncured epoxy composite was cured at 100 °C for 30 min.

2.2 Characterization and measurement

The wetting properties of the surface of basalt fibers were measured by Washburn test using force tensiometer (Sigma700, Biolin Scientific). The wettability to D.I. water was evaluated with 0.5 gram basalt fiber. The structures of basalt fibers were measured by FT-IR (Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy, Frontier, Perkin Elmer) using an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode. The rheological properties and dynamic mechanical thermal properties of basalt fiber-epoxy composite were analyzed by using rheometer (MCR502, Anton Paar) with a solid rectangular fixture. The rheological properties of the basalt fiber-epoxy composite before curing were measured with a disposable aluminium parallel plate of 25 mm diameter at the gap about 0.5 mm. To measure the viscosity rate control mode was chosen in the steady shearing experiment and the range of shear rates was from 1 s⁻¹ to 100 s⁻¹ at 25 °C. Temperature dependence of the viscosity for basalt fiber-epoxy composite was carried out from 30 °C to 130 °C. The frequency sweep was performed in the range of strain 0.4 %, angular frequency 1 Hz to 100 Hz at a shear rate of 0.4 s⁻¹. Temperature sweep test for dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) was ranged from 25 °C to 130 °C with a heating rate 5 °C/min, frequency and strain were 10 Hz and 0.005 %, respectively. The dimensions of the were a width of 10 mm, a length of 50 mm and a thickness of 1 mm. Glass transition is usually investigated by DSC (differential scanning calorimetry, Q25, TA instruments) under nitrogen gas at a heating rate of 5°C/min. All the experiments were performed at a heating rate of at 5 °C/min from 25 to 150 °C under nitrogen gas. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was taken as the midpoint of the heat capacity change during the heating run.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From our previous study, we observed that basalt fibers treated with air plasma become hydrophilic owing to the formation of hydroxyl group onto the fibers. The Washburn method was used to investigate the hydrophilicity of the fibers during the absorption of water. During the test, a cylindrical tube with a permeable filter at the bottom is filled with fiber samples. The bottom of the tube is brought into contact with the wetting liquid so that the fluid can rise into a tube by the capillary force. We observed that water mass by the wetting on the basalt fibers increased differently depending on the fiber coating with different chemical compositions such as melamine, polyvinyl alcohol, and epoxy (Fig. 1). The abbreviations of BF, M, PVA, E, and P represent the Basalt fiber, Melamine, Polyvinyl alcohol, Epoxy, and Plasma, respectively. For instance, BF-P means the basalt fibers treated with air plasma, and BF-P-M represents the composites reinforced with basalt fibers coated with melamine agent.

Fig. 1. Wettability of basalt fibers with and without surface treatment by various chemical agents and air plasma process. The basalt fibers gain mass by absorbing water.

FT-IR analysis was carried out to investigate the presence of chemical coating on the surface of basalt fibers (data not included here). The basalt fibers coated with melamine (e.g., BF-M and BF-P-M) have an absorption peak at 3316 cm^{-1} due to the NH_2 stretching vibrations, which is the typical feature of melamine. The peak at 1664 cm^{-1} is a deformation vibration of N-H, and the 1174 cm^{-1} is attributed to a rock vibration of NH_2 , and the 1046 cm^{-1} peak is due to C-N stretching vibration. The peaks at 1549 and 813 cm^{-1} are assigned to absorption of triazine rings. The infrared spectra of BF-PVA and BF-P-PVA contain major peaks related to hydroxyl and acetate groups. The broad band observed 3300 cm^{-1} is linked to the stretching O-H. The vibrational band observed 2939 cm^{-1} refers to the stretching C-H from alkyl groups, and the peak at 1713 and 1084 cm^{-1} is due to the stretching C=O and C-O stretching vibration. A band was observed due to the C-H deformation vibration 1428 cm^{-1} . For the BF-E- and BF-P-E, the peaks at 2924 and 2854 cm^{-1} are observed to be stretching C-H of CH^2 and CH aromatic and aliphatic, and the peak at 1607 cm^{-1} is stretching C=C of aromatic rings. C-O and C-O-C stretching is observed at 915 and 823 cm^{-1} , respectively. Based on the FT-IR results, we anticipate that the basalt fibers are adequately coated with different chemical agents upon the plasma treatment prior to coating the agents. Two different bonding features are compared in Fig. 2. Without a plasma treatment, the basalt fibers are weakly bonded with chemical agents (physically bonded) while a robust physicochemical bonding takes place after the plasma treatment on the fibers.

Fig. 2. A comparison of two different bonding on basalt fiber: (a) different chemicals are weakly bonded by physical bonding, and (b) strongly bonded by the physicochemical reaction.

Fig. 3 shows the schematic illustration of rheological test of un-cured and cured epoxy composite samples by conventional rheometry. Un-cured epoxy composites are viscous and steady shear viscosity of the samples are measured. On the other hand, cured epoxy composites are semi-rigid and their viscoelastic properties can be measured.

Fig. 3. A schematic illustration of the rheological test of (a) un-cured and viscous epoxy composites and (a) cured and solid epoxy composites.

Fig. 4 represents the variation of viscosity of basalt fiber reinforced epoxy composites as a function of shear rate. We observed that the viscosity of the composites reinforced with plasma treated basalt fibers is higher than those of untreated basalt fibers. That is, the viscosity of the composites with physicochemically (strongly) bonded fibers was more improved than the composite with physically (weakly) bonded fibers, which may be due to the reduction of free volume in the system giving rise to steric hindrance. The plasma enhanced basalt fibers exhibit stronger bonding to the epoxy matrix than the others. From this point of view, the bonding between the basalt fibers and the matrix can be improved by different ways of chemical functionalization.

Fig. 4. Viscosities of various epoxy composites with respect to different chemical agents and plasma treatment.

Fig. 5. Viscosities of un-cured epoxy composites (a) with plasma treatment and (b) without plasma treatment on basalt fibers.

Fig. 5 shows the viscosity of basalt fiber reinforced epoxy composites with respect to temperature increase. We observed that the viscosity of the composites with plasma treatment (e.g., BF-P-E) was higher than those without plasma treatment (e.g., BF-E). Also, the curing process for the BF-P-E sample occurred at a lower temperature in comparison with the BF-E. Therefore, we conclude that the plasma treatment can enhance the processability and fluidic property of un-cured epoxy composites. ,

Fig. 6. DSC traces of epoxy composites (a) without plasma treatment and (b) with plasma treatment after a curing process. A red arrow indicated the glass transition temperature.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) of epoxy composites after a curing process is investigated in Fig. 6. The addition of basalt fibers induces the increase of glass transition temperature, which is attributed by the mobility inhibition of polymer chains in the epoxy matrix by the reinforcing fillers. As shown in Fig. 6(a), the pure epoxy resin (denoted as R) has the glass transition temperature of 69.3 °C, and the glass transition temperature increased to 70.9 °C by introducing basalt fibers in the matrix. This result demonstrates that the mobility of epoxy polymer chains is effectively limited. The glass transition temperature changes little depending on the chemical agents such as E, M, and PVA, indicating that the glass transition temperature is highly related to the heterogeneous phase, in this case basalt fibers, rather than the interphases in between the matrix and the fillers. The glass transition temperature of the composites reinforced with plasma treated basalt fibers is found to be higher than that without plasma treated basalt fibers. That is, the interfacial adhesion between heterogeneous phases is enhanced by the plasma treatment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lee DJ, Song YS. Thermomechanical anisotropy and flowability of talc and glass fiber reinforced multiphase polymer composites. *Composite structures*, 2017;174.
- [2] Shi D, Lian J, He P, Wang LM, Xiao F, Yang L, et al. Plasma coating of carbon nanofibers for enhanced dispersion and interfacial bonding in polymer composites. *Applied physics letters*, 2003;83:5301–3.
- [3] Butylene P, Composites T, Grande M De, International SG. Study of interphase in glass fiber–reinforced poly (butylene terephthalate) composites, *Polymer*, 2004;25:12–25.
- [4] Weikart CM, Miyama M, Yasuda HK. Surface modification of conventional polymers by depositing plasma polymers of trimethylsilane and of trimethylsilane + O₂. II. Dynamic wetting properties. *Journal of colloid interface and science* 1999;211:28–38.
- [5] Pak S, Park S, Song YS, Lee D. Micromechanical and dynamic mechanical analyses for characterizing improved interfacial strength of maleic anhydride compatibilized basalt fiber/polypropylene composites. *Composite structures*, 2018;193..
- [6] Liston EM, Martinu L, Wertheimer MR. Plasma surface modification of polymers for improved adhesion: a critical review. *Journal of adhesion science and technology*, 1993;7:1091–127.